

LARYNGITIS

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Abstract: *Laryngitis (Greek: "larynx ") is an inflammation of the mucous membranes of the larynx, usually associated with colds or infectious diseases such as measles, scarlet fever, and pertussis. The development of the disease can be caused by cooling, overheating (eating cold or hot food), breathing through the mouth, dust in the air, tension in the throat.*

Key words: *Laryngitis, children, breathe, medicine*

Laryngitis is primarily a disease of children. This is because of the differences in the size of the airways in children and adults. In children, the laryngeal cavity is very small, and even mild inflammation can lead to significant narrowing - stenotic laryngitis. In adults, inflammation of the laryngeal mucosa rarely causes severe narrowing of the laryngeal cavity, making laryngitis much easier.

SYMPTOMS OF LARYNGITIS

The first and most obvious sign of laryngitis in children is hoarseness. In addition, the early stages of the disease are accompanied by a dry cough, pain when swallowing and difficulty breathing.

The following symptoms also indicate the development of laryngitis:

Redness and swelling of the throat;

A dog-like cough;

Temperature rise to 37.5-38 ° C;

Dryness and itching in the mouth;

Spasms of the laryngeal muscles.

In general, the symptoms of laryngitis are quite similar to the development of other infectious diseases. But voice problems and whooping cough are specific symptoms of the disease, allowing an error-free diagnosis of laryngitis in almost all cases.

SYMPTOMS OF LARYNGITIS IN NEWBORN BABIES AND BABIES

While older children can complain of sore throats, pain symptoms, and other causes of illness, everything is much more complicated with babies. They cannot express problems verbally. Therefore, the symptoms of laryngitis in infants should be

visually identified. Parents should be aware of the baby's irritability, restlessness, and general weakness, hoarseness and difficulty breathing when crying, as well as coughing and runny nose. All of this is a good reason to see a doctor, and if the disease is diagnosed in time, serious complications can be prevented.

TREATMENT OF LARYNGITIS IN CHILDREN

The treatment of laryngitis is based on three main directions:

Child care routine;

Medicines;

Physiotherapeutic treatments.

PROCEDURE FOR CARE IN LARYNGITIS

If the throat is inflamed, the child should follow a certain lifestyle. The most important are bed rest and limited vocal activity. Of course, you cannot force a child to be silent for a week, but you should try to teach them to whisper if necessary. In this case, the hiccups recover quickly enough, and the child has zero chance of developing irreparable defects in the vocal cords, which are still developing.

The air in the child's room should be cool and humid. Optimal temperature -18 ° C, humidity - 70%. To ensure this, ventilate the room, turn off the heaters if necessary, and use a humidifier.

In laryngitis, eating should not affect the throat. It is neither hot nor cold, nor sour. The throat needs to rest completely. At the same time, drink plenty of fluids (which are not effective). This approach allows you to quickly get through the dry cough phase and reduce the effects of toxins on the body.

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